

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL for article:

**What does the wage structure depend on? Evidence from the national salary survey in Spain
(pending full citation)**

Table a.- NACE recoded to NACE_EWCS

Sections	Title	EWCS
A	Agriculture, forestry, and fishing	1. Agriculture
B	Mining and quarrying	2. Industry
C	Manufacturing	
D	Electricity, gas, steam and air-conditioning supply	
E	Water supply, sewerage, waste management, and remediation	
F	Construction	3. Construction
G	Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	4. Trade and hospitality
I	Accommodation and food service activities	
H	Transportation and storage	5. Transportation
K	Financial and insurance activities	6. Administrative, auxiliary and financial activities
L	Real estate activities	
O	Public administration and defense, compulsory social security	7. Public administration and defense
P	Education	8. Education
Q	Human health and social work activities	9. Healthcare
J	Information and communication	10. Other services
M	Professional, scientific, and technical activities	
N	Administration and support service activities	
R	Arts, entertainment and recreation	
S	Other services	

Table b.- CNO recoded to CNO_EWCS

Sections	Title	CNO_EWCS
A	Directors and managers	1. Directors and managers
B	Scientific and intellectual technicians and professionals	2. Scientific and intellectual technicians and professionals
C	Other scientific and intellectual technicians and professionals	
D	Technicians; support professionals	3. Technicians; support professionals
E	Office employees who do not deal with the public	4. Accounting and administrative employees
F	Customer service clerks	
G	Catering and trade service workers	5. Workers in catering, personal, and protection services
H	Health services and personal care workers	
I	Protective and security services workers	
J	Skilled agricultural, livestock, forestry and fishery workers	6. Skilled agricultural, livestock, forestry and fishery workers

K	Skilled construction workers, except machinery operators	7. Skilled manufacturing industry and construction craftspersons and workers
L	Skilled manufacturing industry workers, except installation and machine operators	
M	Stationary plant and machinery operators, and assemblers	8. Plant and machine operators, and assemblers
N	Mobile machine drivers and operators	
O	Unskilled services workers (except transport)	9. Elementary occupations
P	Agricultural, fishing, construction, manufacturing and transport industry laborers	
Q	Armed forces occupations	Missing values

Table c.- CNO_EWCS recoded to CNO_Toeh

Sections	Title	CNO_EWCS
1	Directors and managers	I Higher controllers
2	Scientific and intellectual technicians and professionals	II Lower controllers
3	Technicians; support professionals	III Routine non-manual employees
4	Accounting and administrative employees	
5	Workers in catering, personal, and protection services	
6	Skilled agricultural, livestock, forestry and fishery workers	V Skilled manual workers
7	Skilled manufacturing industry and construction craftspersons and workers	
8	Plant and machine operators, and assemblers	
9	Elementary occupations	VI Semi and unskilled manual workers

Table d: Descriptive statistics of continuous variable (EES 2006)

		N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Dependent Variable	intCOMSALnoTTplus	235272	.00	1.00	.2420	.20795
	intCOMSALnoTTplus=intCOMSALnoTT+0.00001					
Covariate	antigu10	235272	.01	5.70	.8130	.96245
	antigu10=antigu/10					
	SALOCTBR1K	235272	.01	22.15	1.5398	1.01639
	SALOCTBR1K=SALOCTBR/1000					
intCOMSALnoTTplus: special payments not devoted to shiftwork; antigu10: seniority; SALOCTBR1K: gross pay for the reference month (October)						

Table e: Descriptive statistics of continuous variable (EES 2010)

		N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Dependent Variable	intCOMSALnoTTplus	216769	.00	1.00	.2513	.22465
	intCOMSALnoTTplus=intCOMSALnoTT+0.00001					

Covariate	antigu10 antigu10=antigu/10	216769	.01	5.62	.9252	.96153
	SALOCTBR1K SALOCTBR1K=SALOCT BR/1000	216769	.01	72.41	1.8691	1.36010
intCOMSALnoTTplus: special payments not devoted to shiftwork; antigu10: seniority; SALOCTBR1K: gross pay for the reference month (October)						

Table f: Descriptive statistics of continuous variable (EES 2014)

		N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Dependent Variable	intCOMSALnoTTplus intCOMSALnoTTplus=int COMSALnoTT+0.00001	209362	.00	1.00	.2431	.22020
	antigu10 antigu10=antigu/10	209362	.01	6.00	1.0399	.96924
Covariate	SALOCTBR1K SALOCTBR1K=SALOCT BR/1000	209362	.01	96.09	1.9341	1.44980
	intCOMSALnoTTplus: special payments not devoted to shiftwork; antigu10: seniority; SALOCTBR1K: gross pay for the reference month (October)					

SPSS Syntax

Intensity variables:

- `intSALBASE=SALBASE/ SALOCTBR`
- `intPHEXTRA=PHEXTRA/ SALOCTBR`
- `intCOMSAL=COMSAL/ SALOCTBR`
- `intCOMSALTT=COMSALTT/ SALOCTBR`
- `intCOMSALV=COMSALV/ SALOCTBR`
- `intCOMSALotFIJ=COMSALotFIJ/ SALOCTBR`
- `intCOMSALnoTT=COMSALnoTT/ SALOCTBR`
- `intCOMSALnoTTplus=intCOMSALnoTT+0.00001`
- `intGEXTRA=GEXTRA/ SALBRUTO`
- `intPEXTRAAF=PEXTRAAF/ SALBRUTO`
- `intPEXTRAAV=PEXTRAAV/ SALBRUTO`
- `intVESP=VESP/ SALBRUTO`

Incidence dichotomous variables:

- `dicPHEXTRA= PHEXTRA > 0`
- `dicCOMSAL= COMSAL > 0`
- `dicCOMSALTT= COMSALTT > 0`
- `dicCOMSALV= COMSALV > 0`
- `dicCOMSALotFIJ=COMSALotFIJ > 0`
- `dicCOMSALnoTT=COMSALnoTT > 0`
- `dicGEXTRA=GEXTRA > 0`
- `dicPEXTRAAF= PEXTRAAF > 0`
- `dicPEXTRAAV= PEXTRAAV > 0`
- `dicVESP= VESP > 0`

Descriptive statistics

```
DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=intSALBASE intCOMSAL intCOMSALTT intCOMSALV  
intCOMSALotFIJ intCOMSALnoTT
```

```
intGEXTRA intPEXTRAAF intPEXTRAAV intVESP intPHEXTRA
```

```
/STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV MIN MAX KURTOSIS SKEWNESS.
```

```
DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=dicPHEXTRA dicCOMSAL dicCOMSALTT dicCOMSALV  
dicCOMSALotFIJ dicCOMSALnoTT
```

```
dicGEXTRA dicPEXTRAAF dicPEXTRAAV dicVESP
```

```
/STATISTICS=MEAN
```

GLM

```
GENLIN intCOMSALnoTTplus BY SEXOdic RESPONSA TIPOCON CNACerecodnumEWCS  
CNOrecodTOCH REGULACION3k ESTUrecodnum (ORDER=ASCENDING) WITH antigu10  
SALOCTBR1K
```

```
/MODEL SEXOdic RESPONSA TIPOCON CNACerecodnumEWCS CNOrecodTOCH  
REGULACION3k ESTUrecodnum antigu10 SALOCTBR1K INTERCEPT=YES
```

```
DISTRIBUTION=GAMMA LINK=LOG
```

```
/CRITERIA METHOD=FISHER(1) SCALE=MLE COVB=MODEL MAXITERATIONS=100  
MAXSTEPHALVING=5 PCONVERGE=1E-006(ABSOLUTE) SINGULAR=1E-012  
ANALYSISTYPE=3(WALD) CILEVEL=95 CITYPE=WALD LIKELIHOOD=FULL  
/MISSING CLASSMISSING=EXCLUDE  
/PRINT CPS DESCRIPTIVES MODELINFO FIT SUMMARY SOLUTION  
(EXPONENTIATED).
```

Additional information for Results

Percentage of people having remuneration components and intensity descriptives

EES 2006. ^aPercentage of people having remuneration components and ^bintensity descriptives of remuneration components (% over the total salary)

	% of people ^a	Minimum ^b	Maximum ^b	Mean ^b	Standard deviation ^b	Skewness ^b	Kurtosis ^b
SALBASE	1.0000	.00	1.00	.7352	.2151	-.518	-.669
PHEXTRA	.0661	.00	.70	.0072	.0368	7.011	59.400
COMSAL	.8443	.00	1.00	.2576	.2123	.563	-.587
COMSALTT	.1511	.00	.86	.0156	.0532	5.116	34.793
▪ COMSALV	.2869	.00	1.00	.0557	.1226	2.772	8.283
▪ COMSALotFIJ	.7469	-.04	1.00	.1863	.1956	1.005	.202
COMSALnoTT	.8288	.00	1.00	.2420	.2080	.637	-.472
GEXTRA	.9044	.00	.92	.1469	.0869	.867	2.458
▪ PEXTRAAF	.8925	.00	.77	.1291	.0703	.329	1.697
▪ PEXTRAAV	.2114	.00	.84	.0178	.0525	4.316	23.301
VESP	.1148	.00	.47	.0023	.0139	13.806	276.089
N of valid cases 235272							

ESS 2010. ^aPercentage of people having remuneration components and ^bintensity descriptives of remuneration components (% over the total salary)

	% of people ^a	Minimum ^b	Maximum ^b	Mean ^b	Standard deviation ^b	Skewness ^b	Kurtosis ^b
SALBASE	1	.00	1.00	.7272	.23263	-.490	-.842
PHEXTRA	.0527	.00	.74	.0059	.03496	8.346	84.992
COMSAL	.8031	.00	1.00	.2669	.23028	.524	-.797
COMSALTT	.1581	.00	.90	.0155	.05286	5.334	39.127
COMSALnoTT	.7908	.00	1.00	.2513	.22465	.584	-.721
GEXTRA	.7608	.00	.92	.1184	.09296	.811	1.999
VESP	.1570	.00	.25	.0028	.01447	9.729	120.633
N of valid cases 216769							

ESS 2014 ^aPercentage of people having remuneration components and ^bintensity descriptives of remuneration components (% over the total salary)

	% of people ^a	Minimum ^b	Maximum ^b	Mean ^b	Standard deviation ^b	Skewness ^b	Kurtosis ^b
SALBASE	1	.00	1.00	.7394	.22700	-.550	-.756
PHEXTRA	.0397	.00	.61	.0039	.02601	9.603	113.297
COMSAL	.7998	.00	1.00	.2568	.22550	.577	-.711

COMSALTT	.1462	.00	.81	.0137	.04742	5.213	35.817
COMSALnoTT	.7913	.00	1.00	.2431	.22021	.642	-.613
GEXTRA	.7521	.00	.92	.1145	.09188	.868	2.429
VESP	.2099	.00	.25	.0033	.01418	8.197	88.324
N of valid cases 209436							

GLM parameter estimates EES 2006 according to SPSS reports

Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)	95% Wald Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.		Lower	Upper
(Intercept)	-2.337	.0187	-2.374	-2.301	15585.39	1	.000	.097	.093	.100
[SEXOdic=,00]	.144	.0081	.128	.160	317.045	1	.000	1.155	1.137	1.174
[SEXOdic=1,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[RESPONSA=1]	.037	.0099	.017	.056	13.679	1	.000	1.037	1.017	1.058
[RESPONSA=6]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[TIPOCON=1]	.030	.0086	.013	.047	12.296	1	.000	1.031	1.013	1.048
[TIPOCON=2]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=2,00]	.008	.0112	-.014	.030	.565	1	.452	1.008	.987	1.031
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=3,00]	.266	.0159	.235	.297	279.911	1	.000	1.304	1.264	1.346
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=4,00]	-.071	.0126	-.095	-.046	31.263	1	.000	.932	.909	.955
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=5,00]	.148	.0165	.115	.180	80.212	1	.000	1.159	1.122	1.197
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=6,00]	.082	.0191	.045	.120	18.542	1	.000	1.086	1.046	1.127
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=8,00]	.246	.0190	.209	.284	167.361	1	.000	1.279	1.232	1.328
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=9,00]	.279	.0163	.247	.311	294.010	1	.000	1.322	1.281	1.365
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=10,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[CNOrecodTOCH =1,00]	-.198	.0266	-.250	-.146	55.707	1	.000	.820	.778	.864
[CNOrecodTOCH =2,00]	-.053	.0191	-.091	-.016	7.842	1	.005	.948	.913	.984
[CNOrecodTOCH =3,00]	.042	.0117	.019	.065	12.875	1	.000	1.043	1.019	1.067
[CNOrecodTOCH =5,00]	.046	.0118	.023	.069	15.488	1	.000	1.047	1.024	1.072
[CNOrecodTOCH =6,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[REGULACION3k =1,0]	-.033	.0098	-.052	-.014	11.205	1	.001	.968	.949	.986
[REGULACION3k =2,0]	.036	.0095	.017	.055	14.264	1	.000	1.037	1.017	1.056
[REGULACION3k =3,0]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[ESTUrecodnum=1]	.047	.0119	.024	.070	15.750	1	.000	1.048	1.024	1.073
[ESTUrecodnum=2]	.016	.0133	-.010	.042	1.397	1	.237	1.016	.990	1.043
[ESTUrecodnum=3]	0 ^a	1	.	.
antigu10	.115	.0041	.107	.123	806.163	1	.000	1.122	1.113	1.131
SALOCTBR1K	.336	.0053	.326	.347	3978.488	1	.000	1.400	1.385	1.414
(Scale)	2.663 ^b	.0062	2.651	2.675						

Dependent Variable: intCOMSALnoTTplus=intCOMSALnoTT+0.00001

Model: (Intercept), SEXOdic, RESPONSA, TIPOCON, CNACerecodnumEWCS, CNOrecodTOCH, REGULACION3k, ESTUrecodnum, antigu10, SALOCTBR1K

a. Set to zero because this parameter is redundant.

b. Maximum likelihood estimate.

GLM parameter estimates EES 2010 according to SPSS reports

Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)	95% Wald Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.		Lower	Upper
(Intercept)	-2.136	.0240	-2.183	-2.089	7906.121	1	.000	.118	.113	.124
[SEXOdic=,00]	.138	.0087	.121	.155	252.570	1	.000	1.148	1.129	1.168
[SEXOdic=1,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[RESPONSA=0]	-.057	.0111	-.079	-.035	26.184	1	.000	.945	.924	.965
[RESPONSA=1]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[TIPOCON=1]	.035	.0099	.016	.055	12.804	1	.000	1.036	1.016	1.056
[TIPOCON=2]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=2,00]	.049	.0113	.027	.072	19.104	1	.000	1.051	1.028	1.074
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=3,00]	.312	.0179	.277	.347	303.283	1	.000	1.366	1.319	1.414
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=4,00]	-.094	.0137	-.121	-.067	46.920	1	.000	.910	.886	.935
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=5,00]	.291	.0185	.255	.328	247.652	1	.000	1.338	1.291	1.388
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=6,00]	.035	.0189	-.002	.072	3.393	1	.065	1.035	.998	1.074
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=7,00]	.570	.0197	.532	.609	836.112	1	.000	1.769	1.702	1.839
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=8,00]	.386	.0236	.340	.433	267.104	1	.000	1.472	1.405	1.541
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=9,00]	.255	.0160	.224	.286	255.451	1	.000	1.291	1.251	1.332
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=10,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[CNOrecodTOCH =1,00]	-.181	.0286	-.237	-.125	39.889	1	.000	.835	.789	.883
[CNOrecodTOCH =2,00]	-.024	.0201	-.064	.015	1.474	1	.225	.976	.938	1.015
[CNOrecodTOCH =3,00]	.021	.0135	-.006	.047	2.388	1	.122	1.021	.994	1.049
[CNOrecodTOCH =5,00]	-.016	.0146	-.045	.013	1.191	1	.275	.984	.956	1.013
[CNOrecodTOCH =6,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[REGULACION3k =1,00]	-.094	.0101	-.114	-.074	86.192	1	.000	.910	.892	.928
[REGULACION3k =2,00]	-.047	.0098	-.066	-.028	22.899	1	.000	.954	.936	.973
[REGULACION3k =3,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[ESTUrecodnum=1,00]	.003	.0133	-.023	.029	.054	1	.817	1.003	.977	1.030
[ESTUrecodnum=2,00]	-.018	.0144	-.046	.011	1.486	1	.223	.983	.955	1.011
[ESTUrecodnum=3,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
antigu10	.135	.0044	.126	.143	926.842	1	.000	1.144	1.134	1.154
SALOCTBR1K	.234	.0046	.225	.243	2576.510	1	.000	1.264	1.252	1.275
(Scale)	3.101 ^b	.0075	3.086	3.116						

Dependent Variable: intCOMSALnoTTplus=intCOMSALnoTT+0.00001

Model: (Intercept), SEXOdic, RESPONSA, TIPOCON, CNACerecodnumEWCS, CNOrecodTOCH, REGULACION3k, ESTUrecodnum, antigu10, SALOCTBR1K

a. Set to zero because this parameter is redundant.

b. Maximum likelihood estimate.

GLM parameter estimates EES 2014 according to SPSS reports

Parameter Estimates

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test			Exp(B)	95% Wald Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.		Lower	Upper
(Intercept)	-2.191	.0252	-2.240	-2.141	7540.560	1	.000	.112	.106	.117
[SEXOdic=-,00]	.120	.0088	.102	.137	184.346	1	.000	1.127	1.108	1.147
[SEXOdic=1,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[RESPONSA=0]	-.055	.0121	-.079	-.032	20.865	1	.000	.946	.924	.969
[RESPONSA=1]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[TIPOCON=1]	.067	.0105	.046	.087	40.635	1	.000	1.069	1.047	1.091
[TIPOCON=2]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=2,00]	.051	.0114	.029	.073	19.866	1	.000	1.052	1.029	1.076
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=3,00]	.269	.0184	.233	.305	214.611	1	.000	1.308	1.262	1.356
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=4,00]	-.076	.0138	-.103	-.049	30.287	1	.000	.927	.902	.952
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=5,00]	.230	.0189	.193	.266	147.960	1	.000	1.258	1.212	1.305
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=6,00]	.052	.0193	.014	.089	7.153	1	.007	1.053	1.014	1.093
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=7,00]	.616	.0203	.576	.656	917.414	1	.000	1.852	1.780	1.927
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=8,00]	.376	.0234	.330	.421	256.838	1	.000	1.456	1.390	1.524
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=9,00]	.294	.0163	.262	.325	325.788	1	.000	1.341	1.299	1.385
[CNACerecodnum EWCS=10,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[CNOrecodTOCH =1,00]	-.155	.0290	-.211	-.098	28.486	1	.000	.857	.809	.907
[CNOrecodTOCH =2,00]	-.022	.0200	-.062	.017	1.251	1	.263	.978	.940	1.017
[CNOrecodTOCH =3,00]	-.025	.0141	-.053	.002	3.230	1	.072	.975	.948	1.002
[CNOrecodTOCH =5,00]	-.034	.0152	-.063	-.004	4.929	1	.026	.967	.939	.996
[CNOrecodTOCH =6,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[REGULACION3k =1]	-.073	.0103	-.093	-.052	49.484	1	.000	.930	.911	.949
[REGULACION3k =2]	-.049	.0099	-.068	-.029	24.292	1	.000	.952	.934	.971
[REGULACION3k =3]	0 ^a	1	.	.
[ESTUrecodnum=1,00]	.033	.0127	.009	.058	6.917	1	.009	1.034	1.009	1.060
[ESTUrecodnum=2,00]	.039	.0167	.006	.072	5.498	1	.019	1.040	1.006	1.074
[ESTUrecodnum=3,00]	0 ^a	1	.	.
antigu10	.131	.0045	.122	.140	838.004	1	.000	1.140	1.130	1.150
SALOCTBR1K	.221	.0046	.212	.230	2357.419	1	.000	1.248	1.237	1.259
(Scale)	3.095 ^b	.0076	3.080	3.110						

Dependent Variable: intCOMSALnoTTplus=intCOMSALnoTT+0.00001

Model: (Intercept), SEXOdic, RESPONSA, TIPOCON, CNACerecodnumEWCS, CNOrecodTOCH, REGULACION3k, ESTUrecodnum, antigu10, SALOCTBR1K

a. Set to zero because this parameter is redundant.

b. Maximum likelihood estimate.